

Robust Stability of Barrier-Based Model Predictive Control: Supplementary Material

Panagiotis Petsagkourakis, *Student Member, IEEE*, William P. Heath, *Member, IEEE*, Joaquin Carrasco, *Member, IEEE* and Constantinos Theodoropoulos

Abstract—Conditions for robust input-output stability of barrier-based model predictive control of linear systems with linear and convex nonlinear (hard or soft) constraints are established through the construction of integral quadratic constraints (IQCs). The IQCs can be used to determine sufficient conditions for global closed-loop stability. In particular conditions for robust stability can be obtained in the presence of unstructured model uncertainty. IQCs with both static and dynamic multipliers are developed and appropriate convex searches for the multipliers are presented. The effectiveness of the robust stability analysis is demonstrated through an illustrative numerical example.

APPENDIX A

The parameter m that makes the slope of the nonlinearity tighter seems to be able to significantly reduce conservatism. The corresponding optimization problem is not convex and this may complicate the algorithm. Nevertheless, here we demonstrate that even though the problem is not convex it can have only one solution in the feasible region. The parameter m can be calculated by minimizing the smallest eigenvalue of the Hessian of the barrier inside the feasible region. This problem can be formulated as:

$$\begin{aligned} m &= \min_{u,x} x^T \nabla_u^2 B(u) x \\ \text{s.t. } & x^T x = 1 \\ & Lu \leq b \end{aligned} \quad (\text{A})$$

where

$$\nabla_u^2 B(u) = \sum_i \frac{1}{(b_i - L_i u)^2} L_i^T L_i$$

The KKT conditions of this problem can be written as the following set of equations:

$$\sum_i \frac{1}{(b_i - L_i u)^2} L_i^T L_i x - \lambda x = 0 \quad (\text{Ba})$$

$$1 - x^T x = 0 \quad (\text{Bb})$$

$$\sum_i \frac{1}{(b_i - L_i u)^3} L_i^T x L_i^T L_i x - \sum_i \frac{\lambda_i^{\text{in}}}{2} L_i^T = 0 \quad (\text{Bc})$$

$$\lambda_i^{\text{in}} (L_i^T u - b) = 0 \quad (\text{Bd})$$

This set of equations corresponds to the minimum of the smallest eigenvalue. The optimum objective function will be equivalent to the parameter m used in our analysis. This optimization, however, as is non-convex in the general case can be a bottleneck for the conservatism of the proposed analysis. Here a result regarding the box constraints is provided as well as a relaxation for the general case of bounded constraints. Box constraints can be seen as

$$L = \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ -1 & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 1 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & -1 & \dots & 0 \\ & \vdots & & \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & 1 \\ 0 & 0 & \dots & -1 \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{C})$$

$$b = \begin{bmatrix} \bar{b}_1 \\ \underline{b}_1 \\ \vdots \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{D})$$

(Bc) of the KKT conditions assuming the solution can never be in the bound of the polyhedral, can be written as:

$$-\frac{1}{(\underline{b}_i + u_i)^3} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ x_i^2 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} + \frac{1}{(\bar{b}_i - u_i)^3} \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ \vdots \\ x_i^2 \\ \vdots \\ 0 \end{bmatrix} = 0 \quad (\text{E})$$

The solution of (E) is unique and independent of x . Precisely, the value of m is calculated as:

$$\min \left[\frac{1}{8(\bar{b}_1 + \underline{b}_1)^2}, \dots, \frac{1}{8(\bar{b}_i + \underline{b}_i)^2}, \dots, \frac{1}{8(\bar{b}_N + \underline{b}_N)^2} \right].$$

Nevertheless, the previous case accounts only box constraints, and a decomposition for the staged constraints is next considered. The Hessian can be decomposed using (34) as:

$$\nabla_u^2 B(u) = \begin{bmatrix} \sum_{i=1}^{n_u} \frac{\tilde{L}_0^T \tilde{L}_0}{(\tilde{b}_0 - \tilde{L}_{0i} u_0)^2} & 0 & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & \sum_{i=1}^{n_u} \frac{\tilde{L}_1^T \tilde{L}_1}{(\tilde{b}_1 - \tilde{L}_{1i} u_1)^2} & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & 0 & 0 & \ddots \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{F})$$

Therefore, since (F) has block diagonal structure, the eigenvalues can be found separately for each block using (A), and the smallest one can be selected as m

APPENDIX B

The KKT conditions for u_i with $i = 0, \dots, N_L - 1$ are

$$\begin{aligned} u_i - \theta' + \mu \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_0} \nabla \bar{B}_{ij} - \frac{L_{ij}^T}{b_{ij}} \right) + L_i^{cT} z_i &= 0 \\ L_i^c u_i &= 0 \end{aligned} \quad (\text{G})$$

with

$$z_i = -L_i^c \theta' \quad (\text{H})$$

for $i = 0..N_L - 1$. Summing (G) over i together with (H) gives

$$\begin{aligned} u - (N_L - 1)\theta' + \sum_{i=0}^{N_L-1} \mu \left(\sum_{j=1}^{N_0} \nabla \bar{B}_{ij}(u_i) - \frac{L_{ij}^T}{b_{ij}} \right) &= \\ &= \sum_{i=0}^{N_L-1} L_i^{cT} L_i^c \theta' = (N_L - 2)\theta' \end{aligned} \quad (\text{I})$$

Therefore

$$u - \theta' + \mu \nabla B(u) = 0 \quad (\text{J})$$

APPENDIX C

v_i is bounded, n -cyclic monotone and slope restricted with slope (I). Corollary VI.2 gives the result.

APPENDIX D

$\phi(\theta)$ can be expressed with respect to $\psi(\theta')$, using (33), as a result

$$\Pi(z) = \begin{bmatrix} I & I - \tilde{H} \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}^T \Pi_\psi(z) \begin{bmatrix} I & I - \tilde{H} \\ 0 & I \end{bmatrix}$$

To complete the proof, we use the fact that

$$\bar{L}_i^T \bar{L}_i = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & & & & \\ & \ddots & & & \\ & & I & & \\ & & & \ddots & \\ & & & & 0 \end{bmatrix} \Bigg\} i^{\text{th}} \text{ row}$$

APPENDIX E

Nonlinearity ϕ has the following M_ϕ according to eq. (41): $M_\phi^{11} = 0$,

$$M_\phi^{12} = \begin{bmatrix} R_0 & \dots & R_{N_{ZF}} \\ \vdots & & \\ R_{-N_{ZF}} & & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}$$

and

$$M_\phi^{22} = \begin{bmatrix} R_0 \tilde{H} + \tilde{H} R_0 & \dots & (R_{N_{ZF}} + R_{-N_{ZF}}) \tilde{H} \\ \vdots & & \\ \tilde{H} (R_{N_{ZF}} + R_{-N_{ZF}}) & & \mathbf{0} \end{bmatrix}$$

APPENDIX F

The structure of K is

$$K = \begin{bmatrix} M_1^{11} & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & M_1^{12} & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & M_2^{11} & & & \vdots & 0 & M_2^{12} & & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & & M_{N-1}^{11} & 0 & \vdots & & & M_{N-1}^{12} & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & M_N^{11} & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & M_N^{12} \\ M_1^{12T} & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & M_1^{12} & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 \\ 0 & M_2^{12T} & & & \vdots & 0 & M_2^{12} & & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & \ddots & & \vdots & \vdots & & \ddots & & \vdots \\ \vdots & & & M_{N-1}^{12T} & 0 & \vdots & & & M_{N-1}^{12} & 0 \\ 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & M_N^{12T} & 0 & \dots & \dots & 0 & M_N^{12} \end{bmatrix} \quad (\text{K})$$

APPENDIX G

NOMENCLATURE

- \mathbf{RL}_∞ The space of all real rational transfer functions with no poles on the unit circle
- \mathbf{RH}_∞ Set of rational matrix transfer function matrices without poles outside the unit circle
- $\mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ Set of all real value
- l^m All real-valued sequences
- n_x The size of signal x
- I identity matrix
- A^c For a matrix $A \in \mathbb{R}^{m \times n}$ with rank r we define $A^c \in \mathbb{R}^{n-r \times n}$ such that $A^c A^T = 0$, $A^c A^{cT} = I$
- \bar{A} This is defined as $\begin{cases} (A^c)^c, & \text{when } r < n \\ I, & \text{when } r = n \end{cases}$
- A^* The complex conjugate transpose of the matrix A
- $(f * g)_i$ The discrete convolution at time i is $\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} f_k g_{i-k}$.
- $\sqrt{\langle f, f \rangle}$ the l_2 norm $\|f\|_2$
- $\langle f, g \rangle$ is the inner product of real-valued sequences f and g , defined as $\sum_{k=-\infty}^{\infty} f_k^\top g_k = \frac{1}{\pi} \int_{-\pi}^{\pi} \hat{f}(e^{j\omega}) \hat{g}(e^{j\omega}) d\omega$
- $\hat{(\cdot)}$ the Fourier transform of (\cdot)
- G^* The l_2 -adjoint operator of G
- \mathcal{B} Set of all twice continuous differentiable ϑ -self-concordant (strictly) convex barrier functions over \mathcal{U}
- \mathcal{M} The class of discrete-time rational Zames-Falb multipliers that contains all MIMO rational transfer functions $M_{ZF} \in \mathbf{RL}_\infty^{n \times n}$
- \mathcal{U}_i $\{\tilde{u}_i : F_i(\tilde{u}_i) \leq W_i\}$
- \mathcal{U} Input constraints for MPC
- μ Design positive parameter of the Barrier-based MPC
- ∂f the set of all sub-gradients of a function f at x is called the *subdifferential* of f at x
- θ_k Argument of MPC ϕ at time k
- ϕ Nonlinearity of the function $\phi : \mathbb{R}^{n_x} \rightarrow l_2^{n_y}$
- M_{ZF} The class of discrete-time rational Zames-Falb multipliers that contains all MIMO rational transfer functions $M_{ZF} \in \mathbf{RL}_\infty^{n \times n}$